

Multiple Connectivity Solutions to enable Digital Applications for Viticulture

Insights from the COMMECT Living Lab Luxembourg

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Abstract—Viticulture has an essential role in the agricultural sector of Luxembourg. Climate change is challenging the winegrowers' daily life, and exposing vines to extreme weather conditions and frequent disease occurrence. Drought stress and higher disease severity (mainly Downy Mildew fungus) can damage the total crop. Thus, monitoring and properly managing the vineyard is of foremost importance. In this paper, we present multiple connectivity solutions proposed by the HEU COMMECT project to enable digital applications for winegrowers. The proposed solutions combine Low Power Wide Area networks (LPWAN), cellular 3G/4G networks, with Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), i.e drones and satellite; to extend last mile coverage over the Living Lab (LL), deployed along the Moselle valley in Luxembourg.

in plant protection practices, and support them toward efficient and sustainable management of the vineyards. Meteorological sensors are installed in pilot vineyards to collect weather information, leaf wetness and soil moisture. Images and videos from the field are collected frequently to provide an inventory of the vineyard with different precision, from small to high spatial resolution. Data from sensors and cameras is collected using Wifi, 4G/5G, LoRaWAN, drones, and satellites, based on their availability, and traffic requirements. Once collected, the data can be processed at the edge, or in the cloud, using different models, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, for providing recommendations to the farmers.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Moselle Valley in Luxembourg produces high-quality wines, and the local economy is heavily dependent on wine production. Thus, adapting to drought stress, maintaining plant health, and protecting vineyards from diseases, such as downy mildew (i.e., *Plasmopara viticola*), is very challenging due to the permanent cultivation of vine. Irrigation, fertilization, and pesticide applications are necessary to control diseases and face weather challenges. However, it has several negative impacts, such as environmental risks and high costs of labour and treatments. Timing and dosing of site-specific activities (spraying and irrigation) are strongly linked to microclimatic conditions and state of plant, since the infection process depends on wetness duration at leaf level, temperature conditions during the wetness/drought period, and state of plant health.

Continuous monitoring of micro-climatic conditions, crops, and plants status through digital applications, can play a key role to face the viticulture challenges. In this context, the Horizon Europe COMMECT project [1] focuses on designing innovative connectivity solutions to extend coverage in rural and remote areas, with the final aim of empowering rural communities. The project adopts a multi-actor approach to identify the end users' needs. Several interviews and workshops were organised by the project partners with winegrowers and relevant stakeholders to collect information on the needs of wineries in Luxembourg, with respect to digital tools for efficient managements of the vineyards. The Living Lab (LL) Luxembourg, namely "Digitalization of Viticulture" is developing connectivity solutions and digital tools to assist winegrowers

II. USE CASES

Two use cases have been identified to support farmers in plants protection, and crops' yield increase. Hereafter, we describe both of them, motivating the needs, and proposing the connectivity solutions which meet the technical requirements.

A. In-Field Microclimate and Crop Monitoring in Vineyards

The availability of a network infrastructure in the vineyards is fundamental to ensure reliable in-situ data collection, and thus, continuous monitoring of meteorological and soil conditions. This data can feed models, like *VitiMeteo* [2], providing accurate predictions of disease severity, and thus offering winegrowers comprehensive and accurate information for their decision-making. To support in-situ data collection

Fig. 1: Connectivity for environmental monitoring.

from different sensors in the field, it is important to design an efficient communication infrastructure, which takes into account network availability in the field, deployments costs, energy consumption, among other requirements.

LoRaWAN technology is one of the proposed solutions to extend connectivity in rural areas (see Fig. 1). It is a low power and wide area communication technology that can cover a dense and long-range network of sensors while ensuring energy efficiency. It is used to create local network of sensors. IoT devices installed in the field collect and send environmental data to the LoRaWAN gateway periodically. The gateway forwards data packets to the servers via a backhauling link: cellular networks or satellite backhauling. Collected data will be sent to VitiMeteo server to feed models predicting disease occurrence. In areas with extended and stable cellular coverage, 3G/4G networks will be used to collect IoT data.

B. Digital Twin for Digitalized Management of Vineyards

A digital representation of the farm (i.e., a Digital Twin, DT) can support farmers in managing their vineyards more efficiently. To build an accurate DT of the vineyard, data with high temporal and high spatial resolution, generated by different sensors and cameras, is needed. From a regional perspective, satellite data, like Sentinel-2, is processed frequently to detect drought stress and sunburns. From a bird eye perspective, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are used to collect images at canopy level, which allow detecting patterns and heterogeneities in the field. Finally, at a more precise scale, cameras mounted on tractors can collect video streams, while farmers perform their daily work. These high-resolution videos and images allow an accurate representation of stems and leaves.

Fig. 2: Connectivity for video acquisition from the tractor.

An extended and reliable connectivity platform is needed for this use case to transmit the video streams collected using a camera mounted on the tractor. Consequently, the vine field should have a network infrastructure with large coverage, and enough bandwidth to upload videos, within the activity period. The connectivity solution for this use case is composed of Wi-Fi Access Points (APs), a multi-connectivity smart gateway, and satellite / 5G backhauling as illustrated in Fig. 2. Data is collected by the phone camera mounted on the tractor while the tractor is doing the routine work and navigating between rows. A Wi-Fi network allows to locally process and route data thanks to several APs deployed in the field, whereas

the satellite backhauling network ensures the throughput for transferring the big amounts of data from the smart gateway to the remote data center. The smart gateway ensures a seamless connection by forwarding data received from Wifi APs to the servers via the satellite backhauling link. Afterwards, the data is downloaded to the ground station through the satellite downlink, before finally being uploaded to the data center for cloud-based data processing. Besides satellite, 5G network is another broadband backhauling network option. It can provide higher data transmission rate and lower latency compared to satellite backhauling, when available.

Collected data by the tractor will be combined with data from the UAV and from satellite to create the digital replica of the vineyard. This data can be used to simulate the growth and development of vines in real time. Thus, the operations done in field can be optimized and preventive actions can be performed promptly. The models developed in the DT can predict disease occurrence, fertilization needs, drought severity, and consequently provide timely recommendation to the winegrowers to optimize the interventions and protect their vines.

Fig. 3: (a) Weather station; and (b) camera and antenna mounted on the tractor.

III. CONCLUSION

Terrestrial cellular (4G/5G) and non-cellular (LoRaWAN) networks, combined with NTN, like satellites and UAVs, can extend coverage in large agriculture fields and support the collection of massive in-situ and remote sensing data. In this paper we have presented the use cases and applications identified in the COMMECT LL Luxembourg, aiming at monitoring micro-climate conditions, and building a DT of the vineyards. The proposed connectivity solutions are currently under deployment in the LL, and their performance will be evaluated in future work.

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